

1. Taking a student on a school camp or excursion

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
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2. Helping a student to use their inhaler during an asthma attack

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
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3. Calming a student when they have the difficulty in breathing

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4. Keeping asthma from getting worse when the student starts to wheeze or cough

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
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5. Handling an asthma attack rather than taking the student to the hospital

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
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6. Giving the appropriate medications to the student during an asthma attack

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7. Knowing when the student requires medical assistance

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8. Helping a student avoid things they are allergic to

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9. Your overall confidence in managing children with asthma

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Sum = ()